

INTERCULTURAL ARTISTIC RELATIONS IN THE WORK OF ALEXANDER FEINBERG (ON THE EXAMPLE OF THE RUSSIAN AND UZBEK LITERARY ENVIRONMENT)

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Annotatsiya. Mazkur maqolada Aleksandr Faynberg ijodida madaniyatlararo badiiy muloqot masalasi tahlil qilinadi. Tadqiqotda shoirning rus va o'zbek adabiy muhiti o'rtasidagi ijodiy aloqalarni mustahkamlashdagi o'rni, uning she'riyati va tarjimalarida madaniyatlararo uyg'unlik qanday aks etgani yoritiladi. Shuningdek, Faynberg ijodining ikki xalq adabiy an'analari o'rtasida ma'naviy ko'prik vazifasini bajargani ilmiy jihatdan asoslab beriladi.

Kalit so'zlar. Aleksandr Faynberg, madaniyatlararo muloqot, tarjima san'ati, rus adabiyoti, o'zbek adabiyoti, badiiy aloqalar, poetika, adabiy integratsiya.

Annotation. This article analyzes the issue of intercultural artistic dialogue in the work of Alexander Feinberg. The study highlights the poet's role in strengthening creative ties between the Russian and Uzbek literary environments, how intercultural harmony is reflected in his poetry and translations. It also scientifically substantiates the fact that Feinberg's work serves as a spiritual bridge between the literary traditions of the two peoples.

Keywords. Alexander Feinberg, intercultural dialogue, the art of translation, Russian literature, Uzbek literature, artistic ties, poetics, literary integration.

Аннотация. В данной статье анализируется вопрос межкультурного художественного диалога в творчестве Александра Файнберга. Исследование освещает роль поэта в укреплении творческих связей между русской и узбекской литературными средами, как межкультурная гармония отражается в его поэзии и переводах. Также научно обосновывается тот факт, что

творчество Файнберга служит духовным мостом между литературными традициями двух народов.

Ключевые слова: Александр Файнберг, межкультурный диалог, искусство перевода, русская литература, узбекская литература, художественные связи, поэтика, литературная интеграция.

Introduction. Literature is an important spiritual tool that strengthens cultural ties between peoples. In particular, through the art of translation, the literature of different nations comes closer to each other and is mutually enriched. In this regard, intercultural artistic dialogue is one of the important research areas in literary studies. The work of Alexander Feinberg is a vivid example of this process. The poet made a great contribution to the development of creative ties between the Russian and Uzbek literary environments not only through his poetry, but also through his translation activities.

In the 20th century, a joint cultural life of representatives of different nationalities took shape on the territory of Uzbekistan. This process was also reflected in literature. The connections between Russian and Uzbek literature served to give rise to new creative directions. Alexander Feinberg is one of the poets who worked in this cultural environment. His poetry, along with Russian poetic traditions, also embodies the influence of Uzbek culture and life environment. Therefore, the harmony of the two cultures is clearly visible in the poet's work. One of the important aspects of Feinberg's work is his translation activity. The poet translated the works of many representatives of Uzbek literature into Russian. This served to make Uzbek literature accessible to a wider circle of readers. In the translation process, the poet sought to preserve not only the content of the text, but also its artistic spirit. This makes his translations literary valuable. As a result, Feinberg's work served to strengthen the cultural dialogue between Russian and Uzbek literary traditions. In the poetry of Alexander Feinberg, intercultural harmony is manifested not only at the level of the subject, but also in poetic style. In the poet's poems, human values, philosophy of life, and spiritual experiences are expressed in a common humanistic spirit. This makes his work understandable and close to representatives of different cultures. The poet's artistic thinking goes beyond national boundaries and embodies common ideas inherent in humanity.

In conclusion, the work of Alexander Feinberg is one of the most important examples of intercultural artistic dialogue between the Russian and Uzbek literary environments. The poet, through his poetry and translation activities, created a spiritual bridge between the literatures of the two peoples. Feinberg's work is of great importance as a literary heritage that served the process of mutual understanding and artistic enrichment between different cultures.

Kirish. Adabiyot xalqlar o'rtasidagi madaniy aloqalarni mustahkamlovchi muhim ma'naviy vosita hisoblanadi. Ayniqsa, tarjima san'ati orqali turli millatlar adabiyoti bir-biri bilan yaqinlashadi va o'zaro boyiydi. Shu jihatdan madaniyatlararo badiiy muloqot adabiyotshunoslikda muhim tadqiqot yo'nalishlaridan biridir. Aleksandr Faynberg ijodi ham aynan mana shu jarayonning yorqin namunasidir. Shoir nafaqat o'z she'riyati bilan, balki tarjima faoliyati orqali ham rus va o'zbek adabiy muhirlari o'rtasidagi ijodiy aloqalarni rivojlantirishga katta hissa qo'shgan.

XX asrda O'zbekiston hududida turli millat vakillarining birgalikdagi madaniy hayoti shakllandi. Bu jarayon adabiyotda ham o'z aksini topdi. Rus va o'zbek adabiyotlari o'rtasidagi aloqalar yangi ijodiy yo'nalishlarning paydo bo'lishiga xizmat qildi. Aleksandr Faynberg ana shu madaniy muhitda ijod qilgan shoirlardan biridir. Uning she'riyati rus poetik an'analari bilan bir qatorda o'zbek madaniyati va hayotiy muhitining ta'sirini ham o'zida mujassam etadi. Shu sababli shoir ijodida ikki madaniyat uyg'unligi yaqqol ko'zga tashlanadi. Faynberg ijodining muhim jihatlaridan biri uning tarjima faoliyatidir. Shoir ko'plab o'zbek adabiyoti namoyandalarining asarlarini rus tiliga tarjima qilgan. Bu esa o'zbek adabiyotining kengroq o'quvchilar doirasiga yetib borishiga xizmat qilgan. Tarjima jarayonida shoir nafaqat matn mazmunini, balki uning badiiy ruhini ham saqlashga intilgan. Bu esa uning tarjimalarini adabiy jihatdan qimmatli qiladi. Natijada Faynberg ijodi rus va o'zbek adabiy an'analari o'rtasidagi madaniy muloqotni mustahkamlashga xizmat qilgan. Aleksandr Faynberg she'riyatida madaniyatlararo uyg'unlik nafaqat mavzu darajasida, balki poetik uslubda ham namoyon bo'ladi. Shoir she'rlarida insoniy qadriyatlar, hayot falsafasi va ma'naviy kechinmalar umumiy gumanistik ruhda ifodalanadi. Bu esa uning ijodini turli madaniyat vakillari uchun tushunarli va yaqin qiladi. Shoirning badiiy tafakkuri milliy chegaralardan kengroq bo'lib, insoniyatga xos umumiy g'oyalarni o'zida mujassam etadi.

Xulosa qilib aytganda, Aleksandr Faynberg ijodi rus va o'zbek adabiy muhirlari o'rtasidagi madaniyatlararo badiiy muloqotning muhim namunalaridan biridir. Shoir o'z she'riyati va tarjima faoliyati orqali ikki xalq adabiyoti o'rtasida ma'naviy ko'prik yaratgan. Faynberg ijodi turli madaniyatlar o'rtasidagi o'zaro tushunish va badiiy boyish jarayoniga xizmat qilgan adabiy meros sifatida muhim ahamiyatga ega.

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